

Design of Horseshoe Networks with Low-Loss Filterless Nodes and Point-to-Multipoint Transceivers

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Abstract— This paper proposes a mathematical model to combine the utilization of point-to-multipoint coherent transceivers in horseshoe networks using node architectures based on 2-by-2 couplers and optimized deployment of pre-amplifiers. The results evaluate the pros and cons of this architecture compared to pairing 1-by-2 splitters/combiners.

Keywords—point-to-multipoint transceivers, optical coupler

I. INTRODUCTION

Metro-aggregation networks connect access networks to metro-core networks and have specific requirements, such as a hub-and-spoke traffic pattern, survivability to single failures, and total capacity requirements that fall between those of the network segments they interface with. To achieve survivability to single failures, a horseshoe topology can be used, connecting each leaf node to two different hub nodes [1]. Compared to standard coherent point-to-point (P2P) transceivers, coherent point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transceivers – enabled by digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) – present two advantages in this scenario: (i) they inherently support a hub-and-spoke traffic pattern, and (ii) they provide a more economical migration from direct to coherent detection. A single high-capacity device at a hub connects to several lower-capacity devices at leaf nodes using these P2MP transceivers [2]. Filterless architectures simplify networks by replacing active filter cards with passive devices while deploying optical amplifiers selectively. The authors of [1] propose an integer linear programming (ILP) model to design horseshoe networks using P2MP transceivers, minimizing amplifiers while meeting end-to-end performance criteria. That work assumes leaf nodes are customizable by selecting each splitter and combiner from a catalog. Although this allows to maximize amplifier savings, it requires more components and leads to a more complex and error-prone deployment. In [3], a few pre-defined node architectures have been investigated to simplify the process of planning and optimizing the network.

The 1-by-2 splitter and combiner-based node architecture optimization framework initially proposed in [1] is modified to model the utilization of a single 2-by-2 coupler, as shown in Fig. 1, instead of splitter and combiner pairs. The resulting 2-by-2 coupler-based architecture is simpler, requiring only one device per direction and leaf node, although potentially less flexible. This paper assesses how both architectures compare when considering different ratios. Note that 2-by-2 couplers are typically made by intertwining, stretching, and fusing two parallel optical fibers, while 1-by-2 splitters/combiners can be realized by terminating one of the ports internally.

Fig 1. 2-by-2 coupler-based node architecture

II. OPTIMIZATION FRAMEWORK

Each optical fiber delivers downstream traffic from one hub node and upstream traffic towards the other one in a filterless horseshoe network. Each leaf node comprises one coupler per transmission direction. It is assumed that a pre-amplifier can be present in each direction and minimizing the number of these devices is the main optimization objective. The main model's constraints to ensure a feasible solution are; (i) the receiver sensitivity, (ii) maintaining low power across optical fibers to ensure negligible nonlinearity interference (NLI), and (iii) not exceeding the maximum tolerable power difference between subcarriers (SCs) at the hub's receiver (henceforth, designated as the SCs power difference). Tables I and II present the main input parameters and the variables of the ILP model.

TABLE I. MODEL INPUT PARAMETERS

Parameter	Description and values assumed
$G(V, E)$	graph with leaf nodes $u, u_p, v \in V$ and links $l \in E$
$W(u)$	length of the link preceding leaf node u
α	fiber attenuation coefficient (0.22 dB/km)
$G_s(g)$	amplifier gain, $\{0, 6, 7, \dots, 20\}$ dB, where g is the gain index
P_{sc}	transmitter launch power per SC (m-12 dBm)
P_n	power threshold for negligible NLI per SC (-10 dBm)
P_s	receiver sensitivity for 16QAM signal (-24 dBm)
P_l	Maximum allowable SCs power difference at the hub (8 dB)
$H(s, p)$	express and add/drop loss of coupler $s + 0.5$ dB excess loss

TABLE II. MODEL VARIABLES

Variable	Description
∇_s^u	binary variable for coupler selection per leaf node
δ_p^u	loss of express and add/drop transmission for leaf node u
μ_g^u	1 if amplifier at leaf u takes gain with index g , otherwise 0
ϕ_u^1	hub 2 receiver power per SC coming from leaf node u
ϕ_u^2	leaf node u receiver power per SC coming from hub 1
ϵ_1 / ϵ_2	lower / upper bound of variables ϕ_u^1

$$\min \sum_u \sum_{G_e(g) \neq 0} \mu_u^g + w[\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1] \quad (1)$$

$$\delta_p^u = \sum_s \nabla_s^u H(s, p), \quad \forall u \in V \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_u^1 = P_{sc} + \sum_{v > u} G_e(g) \mu_g^u - \alpha \sum_{v > u} W(v) - \delta_{add/drop}^u - \sum_{v > u} \delta_{exp}^v, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_u^2 = P_{sc} + \sum_{v < u} G_e(g) \mu_g^u - \alpha \sum_{v < u} W(v) - \delta_{add/drop}^u - \sum_{v < u} \delta_{exp}^v, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (4)$$

$$P_{sc} + \sum_{u_p < v \leq u} \sum_g G_e(g) \mu_v^g - \alpha \sum_{u_p < v \leq u} W(u) - \delta_{add/drop}^u - \sum_{u_p < v \leq u} \delta_{exp}^v \leq P_n, \quad \forall u, u_p \in V \quad (5)$$

$$P_{sc} + \sum_{v \leq u} \sum_g G_e(g) \mu_v^g - \alpha \sum_{v \leq u} W(u) - \sum_{v \leq u} \delta_{exp}^v \leq P_n, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_s \nabla_s^u = 1, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_g \mu_g^u = 1, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (8)$$

$$\epsilon_1 \leq \phi_u^1, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (9)$$

$$\epsilon_2 \geq \phi_u^2, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (10)$$

$$\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1 \leq P_l \quad (11)$$

$$\phi_u^1, \phi_u^2 \geq P_s, \quad \forall u \in V \quad (12)$$

The ILP model has a dual objective (1). Firstly, it aims to minimize the number of amplifiers. Secondly, it tries to reduce the power difference of SCs at hub 2, to optimize performance at the receiver. This is achieved through the weight factor w . Constraints (2) assign losses to express and add/drop ports, while (3) and (4) present the power levels from leaf nodes to hub 2 and from hub 1 to leaf nodes, respectively. Constraints (5) and (6) set launch power thresholds to limit NLI impact for both downstream and upstream signals. Node configuration and amplifier selection are determined by (7) and (8). Constraints (9) to (11) calculate the lower and upper bounds of SC power levels at hub 2 and ensure the SCs power difference is less than the considered threshold. Lastly, receiver sensitivity is enforced by

“90/10”, and “50/50” ratios. Note that in the “All” scenario, all ratios from 10% to 90% with a granularity of 10% are available. For the splitter/combiner-based node, the number of amplifiers increases significantly when fewer ratios are available, and the “50/50” splitter/combiner node leads to the highest number of amplifiers for both 5-leaf (3.9 amplifiers) and 10-leaf (8.5 amplifiers) horseshoes. In contrast to splitter/combiner-based node, balanced “50/50” gives a lower number of amplifiers compared to single unbalanced “90/10” couplers in coupler-based node architecture thanks to the 3.5 dB lower express loss per leaf. Fig. 2(b) shows the average SCs power difference (at hub 2) for the same scenarios. Obviously, all instances are under 8 dB as per constraint (11). But, in general, coupler-based nodes and larger horseshoes result in higher SCs power differences due

Figure 2. (a) Average number of amplifiers and (b) average SCs power difference in 5-leaf and 10-leaf node horseshoe networks.

(12). The ILP model cannot include (nonlinear) constraints for the required optical signal-to-noise ratio (ROSNR), which must be verified as a post-processing step.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ILP model assumes the use of a fully loaded single 400G transceiver at each hub. Additionally, it assumes low-capacity transceiver parameters have similar values for the constraints. The coupler ratios determine the losses of express, and add/drop signals, affecting the optimal number of amplifiers. Therefore, similar to [1], we consider four different sets of coupler ratios as input to the ILP model. We use 25 randomly generated networks (with an average link length of 12 km) to produce the results for each scenario. The values of other parameters are shown in Table I. For simplicity, we focus solely on optimizing the fiber direction from hub 1 to hub 2. Fig. 2(a) shows the average number of amplifiers for the two node architectures and two horseshoe sizes when considering “All”, “70/30 & 90/10”,

to a lower degree of freedom and greater variance from the larger number of leaf nodes. In conclusion, the coupler-based architecture leads to a more compact node solution for horseshoe metro-aggregation networks leveraging P2MP transceivers with almost the same number of amplifiers (even lower if “50/50” ratio if enforced) despite higher SCs power difference (“90/10” ratio is an exception), when compared to the baseline solution that pairs splitters and combiners.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. M. Hosseini, et al., “Optimized design of filterless horseshoe networks exploiting point-to-multipoint coherent transceivers,” *Journal of Optical Communications and Networking*, vol. 15, no. 9, pp. 569-578, 2023.
- [2] D. Welch, et al., “Digital subcarrier multiplexing: Enabling software-configurable optical networks,” *Journal of Lightwave Technology*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 1175-1191, 2022.
- [3] J. Pedro, et al., “Optimal Node Design in Filterless Horseshoe Networks with Point-to-Multipoint Transceivers,” *IEEE Photonics Conference (IPC)*, November 2023.